

COMPETENCE SKILLS OF TEACHERS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS: BASIS FOR CAPABILITY BUILDING ENHANCEMENT PLAN

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Competence Skills of Teachers in Relation to Academic Performance of Pupils: Basis for Capability Building Enhancement Plan

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Abstract

This study examines the competence skills of elementary school teachers in District 4, Schools Division of Bago City, and their relationship to pupils' academic performance, serving as the basis for a capability-building enhancement plan. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study surveyed 140 teachers and analyzed the academic performance of 4,120 pupils. Teacher competence was assessed in five domains: personal skills, management skills, instructional skills, teaching effectiveness, and professionalism. Results revealed that teachers demonstrated a very high level of competence across all domains. Similarly, pupil academic performance was rated as very satisfactory, with an average grade of 85.93. Statistical analysis showed no significant differences in teacher competence when grouped by demographic variables such as sex, age, educational attainment, teaching position, years in service, and training attended. Furthermore, no significant relationship was found between teachers' competence skills and pupils' academic performance. These findings suggest that while teachers exhibit high competence, other factors may influence student achievement. The study recommends continuous professional development programs tailored to teachers' specific training needs, active engagement strategies to enhance pupil learning, and further research incorporating additional variables such as student motivation and home environment. By refining teacher development initiatives, this research aims to support educational stakeholders in fostering an environment conducive to academic excellence.

Keywords: *competence skills, teachers, academic performance, enhancement plan*

Introduction

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) outlines the required skills and competencies of quality teachers, enabling them to cope with the emerging global frameworks. If the required skills and competencies are not met, various professional development interventions will be given to them. PPST helps assure parents and guardians that their children receive quality basic education from qualified professionals whose competencies are abreast with changes and advancements in the information age (deped.gov.ph, 2018). The PPST outlines the required skills and competencies of quality teachers, enabling them to cope with the emerging global frameworks. It basically aims to set the clear expectations of teachers along well-defined career stages of professional development from beginning to distinguished practice, engage teachers to actively embrace a continuing effort in attaining proficiency, and apply a uniform measure to assess teacher performance, identify needs, and provide support for professional development. It targets to produce better teachers in the country by improving their qualifications skills and by increasing their levels of knowledge, practice and professional engagement.

There are various approaches and definitions of the concept of competence. Vitello et al. (2021) defined competence as the ability to incorporate or apply knowledge, skills, beliefs, and attitude consistently while performing in a specific context.

The competence skills of a teacher are a big factor in the academic performance of the pupils. Indeed, the researcher would like to investigate the relationship between the competence skills of teachers and the academic performance of pupils. Competencies of teachers included the personal skills, management skills, instructional skills, teaching effectiveness and professionalism. Though our very year of 2020 is a little challenging as while the technologies are present, teachers and school administrators are dealing with phenomenal pandemic outbreak. Thus, the researcher understand that pupils encounter different kind of teachers. It is a fact that the various level of competence skills of their teacher bears different effects upon their academic performance. Likewise, teacher must be aware of their own level of competency especially during this time of pandemic so as to be extra conscious of how their teaching affects the academic performance of the pupils. The advocacy to promote academic excellence and quality education of the elementary school teachers of District 4, Schools Division of Bago City in view of making the district a center of excellence made the researcher decide to conduct the competence skills of teachers in relation to academic performance of pupils in the said district.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the level competence skills of public elementary school teachers of District 4, Schools Division of Bago City in relation to academic performance of pupils for school year 2022-2023: basis for capability building enhancement plan. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of elementary school teachers of in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;

- 1.3. highest educational attainment;
- 1.4. teaching position;
- 1.5. number of years in service; and
- 1.6. training attended of teachers?
2. What is the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers when taken as a whole and grouped in terms of:
 - 2.1. personal skills;
 - 2.2. management skills;
 - 2.3. instructional skills;
 - 2.4. teaching effectiveness; and
 - 2.5. professionalism?
3. What is the level of pupil's academic performance?
4. Is there a significant difference in the competence skills of elementary school teachers when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers and pupil's academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized the descriptive correlational research design in evaluating the relationship between the level of competence skills of teachers and pupil's academic performance of District 4, Schools Division of Bago City, Negros Occidental. Descriptive correlational design is defined as a type of study that uses standard social research methods for evaluative purposes as a specific research methodology, and as an assessment process that employs special techniques unique to the evaluation of a certain social programs (Hassan, 2023).

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers of District 4, Schools Division of Bago City and their respective pupils. There were 215 teachers in the said division.

The researcher used the stratified random sampling technique first to categorize the respondents per school. Then, simple random sampling technique through lottery method was used to identify respondents to be taken as samples.

Table 1. Distribution of the Elementary School Teachers

<i>School</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
A	8	5
B	12	8
C	21	14
D	19	12
E	25	16
F	7	5
G	6	4
H	13	8
I	9	6
J	22	14
K	15	10
L	58	38
Total	215	140

Instrument

An adoptive questionnaire was used in this study. This survey questionnaire was adopted from Teacher-Competency-Checklist_HHD_adjuncts.doc. The questionnaire has two parts. The first part contains the profile of the respondents such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, teaching position, years in service and training attended of teachers. The second part measures the competencies such as personal skills, management skills, instructional skills, teaching effectiveness and professionalism. It consists of 30 items relevant to the competence skills of teachers of district 4, Schools Division of Bago City. The 30 items are divided into 5 specific skills having 6 items in each skill. Each item can be measured using Likert scale using 5 as very good, 4 as good, 3 as fair, 2 as poor and 1 as very poor. To measure the academic performance of the students, their average grades in the first to fourth quarter was used.

Procedure

The researcher secured permission from the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Bago to conduct this research in District 4. Furthermore, approval of the school principal was secured and the researcher sent letters addressed to teachers to explain the purpose of the survey. The gathered data were tallied, organized, presented and interpreted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences

(SPSS).

Data Analysis

The data were retrieved, encoded, and processed using SPSS. The statistical tools that the researcher used were:

To answer statement of the problem number one which states what is the teacher's profile in terms of: sex, age, highest educational attainment, teaching position and number of years in service, frequency and percentage were used.

To answer statement of the problem number two which states, what is the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers when they are grouped as a whole and as to personal skills, management skills, instructional skills, teaching effectiveness, and professionalism, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem number three which states, what is the level of pupil's academic performance, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem number four which states, is there a significant difference between the profile of the respondent and their competence skills, Mann Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis H test were used.

To answer statement of the problem number five which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers and pupils' academic performance, Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma or Gamma Coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analyses, and interpretation of data. It likewise includes the tables which aid in the analysis and interpretation of data. To determine the level of competence skills of teachers in relation to academic performance of pupils.

Profile of Teachers

There were 140 elementary school teachers of District 4, Schools Division of Bago City who were the respondents of the study.

The table 2 on the next page presents the profile of elementary school teachers.

Based on Table 2, majority of the respondents were female with a frequency of 126 or 90 percent of the total respondents. Regarding their age, most of them are in the age range of 31- 40 years old with a frequency of 61 Or 43.60 percent. 25.00 percent or 35 of them are aged between 41-50 years old. While 30 or 21.40 percent of them are 51 years old and above. The least are those who are aged 30 years old and below with a total of 14 or 10.00 percent of the total respondents.

In terms of their highest educational attainment, majority of the respondents have a bachelor's degree with a frequency of 46 or 32.90 percent followed by those who have units in MA with 41 or 29.30 percent, Car in Ma with 28 or 20.00 percent, Units in doctorate with two (2) or one 1.40 percent, and the remaining one (1) or 0.70 percent with a doctorate degree.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of Public Elementary School Teachers*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Groupings</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Male	14	10.00
	Female	126	90.00
	Total	140	100.00
Age	30 years old & below	14	10.00
	31-40 years old	61	43.60
	41-50 years old	35	25.00
	51 years old & above	30	21.40
	Total	140	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	46	32.90
	W/ Units In MA	41	29.30
	Car in MA	28	20.00
	Master's Degree	22	15.70
	Units in Doctorate	2	1.40
Doctorate Degree	1	0.70	
Total	140	100.00	
Position	Teacher 1	70	50.00
	Teacher 2	21	15.00
	Teacher 3	40	28.60
	Master Teacher 1	7	5.00
	Master Teacher 2	2	1.40
	Total	140	100.00
Service	10 years & below	64	45.70

	11-20 years	41	29.30
	21 - 30 years	24	17.10
	31 years and above	11	7.90
	Total	140	100.00
Training	INSET	66	47.10
	INSET/TIP	74	52.90
	Total	140	100.00

Half of the respondents have a position of teacher 1 with 70 or 50.00 percent. This is followed by the teacher 3 respondents with 40 or 28.60 percent, teacher 2 with 21 or 15.00 percent, master teacher 1 with seven (7) Or 5.00 percent, and mater teacher 2 with two (2) or 1.40 percent.

Regarding their length of service, most of the respondents were teaching 10 years and below with a frequency of 64 or 45.70 percent, 11-20 years with 41 or 29.30 percent, 21-30 years with 24 or 17.10 percent, and those who are teaching 31 years and above with 11 or 7.90 percent of the total respondents.

The training that 74 or 52.90 percent of the respondents have attender is the INSET or TIP training while 66 or 47.10 percent of the respondents have attended the INSET training.

Level of Competence Skill of Teachers

The second objective of this study of this study is to determine the level of competence skills of Elementary School Teachers when they are grouped as a whole and as to personal skills, management skills, instructional skills, teaching effectiveness and professionalism.

Table 3. *Level of Competence Skills of Elementary School Teachers*

<i>Competence Skill</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Personal Skills	140	4.75	Very High
Management Skills	140	4.67	Very High
Instructional Skills	140	4.63	Very High
Teaching effectiveness	140	4.70	Very High
Professionalism	140	4.74	Very High
As a whole	140	4.70	Very High

The table 3 presented above shows that when taken as a whole, the level of competence skills of teachers is very high with a mean of 4.70. In terms of their individual skills, personal skills have the highest mean with 4.75, followed by professionalism with 4.74, teaching effectiveness with 4.70, managerial skills with 4.67, and instructional skills with 4.63. All are interpreted as very high.

The result implies that they are matured and professional enough to handle any situations that may occur in my class, having an initiative in teaching responsibilities, exhibit ability to exercise routine matters with efficiency, organize the class to maximize learning for instructional purposes efficiently, create appropriate environment for learning, can design appropriate learning objectives for each lesson and class, can evaluate the effectiveness of personal teaching practices in terms of objective, use critical thinking to evaluate daily lessons and make needed revisions, utilize variety of teaching strategies and methods rather than one method, exhibit ability to develop cooperative learning opportunities within lessons, display behaviors appropriate to professional status, and use performance and prescriptive feedback appropriately.

The finding of this study is closely similar to the claim of Sancho et al. (2021) that teachers possess high personal skills or soft skills they also have a high self- concept about the level of soft skills development.

Contrary to the results, the study of Salih (2020) states that some teachers are lacking in their personal skills. This includes their communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

In terms of their management skills and instructional skills, Dumaguig (2023) also agrees with the findings. According to him, the management skills of teachers as well as their instructional skills are very high. This means that they have good management inside the classroom and are able to teach effectively.

The results of the study of Oloro also coincides with the results. According to him teachers possess better instructional skills in different aspect of teaching.

With the similar results, Giocomazzi et al. (2023) revealed that teachers were able to show greater ability in their instructional skills. They were able to differentiate rote learning and cognitive thinking. They created lesson plans that are clearer and coherent that develops the critical thinking skills of students as well as improve their learning.

In terms of teaching effectivity, the study of Owodunni & Onanuga (2019) matches with the findings. According to them, teachers have a high teaching effectiveness in different dimensions of teaching such as classroom teaching, materials, student activities, management inside the classroom, personality of the teacher, and the evaluation.

Concurring with the results, the study of Lalchajandami & Lalnunfel (2019) also revealed that majority of the teachers believed that they are highly competent in terms of their teaching effectivity.

On the contrary, Survana & Varun (2023) had a different result wherein most of the teachers believed they had moderate effectivity followed by those who believe that they have high effectivity.

In terms of Professionalism, the study of Erturk (2022) also that teachers possess a high level of autonomy and professionalism as well as dedication to their profession.

Level of Pupil’s Academic Performance

The table presents the level of the academic performance of pupils.

Table 4. *Level of Academic Performance of Pupils*

<i>Level of Academic Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	0		
Very satisfactory	112		
Satisfactory	28	85.93	Very satisfactory
Satisfactory	0		
Did not meet expectation	0		
Total	140		

The table 4 presents the level of academic performance of pupils with an average grade of 85.93 which is interpreted as very satisfactory. Out of 140 respondents, 112 have a very satisfactory performance and 28 are performing satisfactorily. This implies that majority of the pupils are performing well in the class.

The result is supported by the findings of Alib (2023) that the level of academic performance of Grade VI pupils obtained a mean of 87.99 and was interpreted as very satisfactory. This means that the Grade VI pupils are performing well academically.

Additionally, the finding drawn from this study is similar to those of Erojo (2020) who also reported satisfactory academic performance among the 41 feeding recipients, with an average score of 84.4. This suggests that the beneficiaries are capable of competing and excelling academically, despite having received fewer nutrients compared to their peers with normal nutritional status.

Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of their Sex

The table on the next page presents the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their sex.

Table 5. *Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	14	57.14
Female	126	71.98
Total	140	

Computed value (U): 695.00
p-value: 0.191
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5 shows that the female respondents have a mean rank of 57.14 and the male respondents have a mean rank of 71.98 in their competence skill.

Using the Mann Whitney U Test, the computed value of 695.00 was obtained. With the p-value of 0.191 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their sex.

This finding implies that the sex of the teachers do not affect the level of their competence skills. Male and female teachers can both perform proficiently regardless of their sex.

Aban et al. (2020) does not have the same results as presented in this study. In terms of their sex, it was shown that male teachers tend to be less competent compared to female teachers.

Maji (2022) also shares different results wherein he stated that female teachers are more competent and excel more compared to male teachers.

Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of their Age

The table display the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their age.

Table 6 shows that the teachers who are in the age range of 51 years old & above have a mean rank of 76.92 in their competence skills.

The 31-40 years old have a mean rank of 71.34, 41-50 years old range have a mean rank of 69.33, and those who are within the 30 years old and below age have a mean rank of 56.00.

Table 6. *Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of Age*

Age	N	Mean Rank
30 years old & below	14	56.00
31-40 years old	61	71.34
41-50 years old	35	69.33
51 years old & above	30	76.92
Total	140	

Computed value (H): 2.63

p-value: 0.453

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test, the P-value of 0.453 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 and the obtained computed value is 2.63. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. With the resulting data, there is no significant difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their age.

The result implies that the age of teachers do not influence their competence skill. Teachers can be competent regardless of their age. Younger teachers can be as competent as the older ones.

Maji (2022) agrees with the results of this study. According to him older teachers (40 and above) are more competent than younger ones (40 and below).

The study of Mangonon (2021) also conforms the findings of this study. According to him, 21–30-year-old bracket are the age range with more competent teachers.

Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of their Highest Educational Attainment

The table below illustrates the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their highest educational attainment.

Table 7. *Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	N	Mean Rank
Bachelor's Degree	46	64.16
W/ Units In MA	41	75.87
Car in MA	28	70.61
Master's Degree	22	73.39
Units in Doctorate	2	105.5
Doctorate Degree	1	5.50
Total	140	

Computed value (H): 6.08

p-value: 0.299

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

In Table 7, the respondents having units in doctorate show a mean rank of 105.5, followed by those with units in master's degree who display a mean rank of 75.87. Respondents with master's degree have a mean rank of 73.39, those who have a CAR in MA show a mean rank of 70.61, with bachelor's degree have a mean rank of 64.16, and those who are doctorate degree display a mean rank of 5.50.

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test, resulted to a P- value of 0.299 at 0.05 level of significance with a computed value of 6.08 thus, accept the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their highest educational attainment.

The result implies that the competence skills of teachers do not vary when they are grouped in terms of their highest educational attainment. Those who are college graduate can display the competence skills displayed by those who have doctorate degree.

With similar findings, Mangonon (2021) also stated that most of his respondents are have masteral units. They are also very competent.

The results also coincide with the result of Aban et al. (2020) wherein in terms of their highest educational attainment, comparable efficiency was observed.

Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of their Teaching Position

The table presented below shows the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their teaching position.

Table 8 presents that competence skill of the respondents holding a Master Teacher 2 position have a mean rank of 88.25, those who are Master Teacher 1 shows a mean rank of 84.21, Teacher 3 respondents display a mean rank of 72.38, Teacher 1 have a mean rank

of 68.84, and those who are Teacher 2 shows a mean rank of 66.19.

Table 8. Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of Teaching Position

Teaching Position	N	Mean Rank
Teacher 1	70	68.84
Teacher 2	21	66.19
Teacher 3	40	72.38
Master Teacher 1	7	84.21
Master Teacher 2	2	88.25
Total	140	

Computed value (H): 1.64

p-value: 0.801

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test, the computed value is 1.64 and a P- value of 0.801 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, accepting the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their teaching position. The result implies that the competence skills of elementary school teachers is not influenced by their teaching position.

Bogo & Aperocho (2023) also states that in terms of the level of competence of teachers when grouped according to their teaching positions, their results also showed that there was no significant relationship between the two variables.

Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of their Number of Years in Service

The table below display the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their number of years in service.

Table 9. Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of Number of Years in Service

Years in Service	N	Mean Rank
10 years & below	64	68.27
11 - 20 years	41	71.01
21 - 30 years	24	71.46
31 years and above	11	79.45
Total	140	

Computed value (H): 0.76

p-value: 0.860

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table 9 shows that the competence skill of teachers who served for 31 years and above have a mean rank of 79.45, those who are in the service of teaching for 21 - 30 years show a mean rank of 71.46, those who served for 11 - 20 years have a mean rank of 71.01 and those who served for 10 years & below have a mean rank of 68.27.

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test, it resulted to a P- value of 0.860 at 0.05 level of significance with a computed value of 0.76 thus, accepting the null hypothesis. With the resulting data, there is no significant difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of their number of years in service. This implies that the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers do not depend on their number of years in service.

Contrastingly, Aban et al. (2020) states that the length of service of teachers influences their efficiency. Wherein teachers with the shortest teaching experience also have a lower competence compared to those who have longer length in terms of service.

Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of their Trainings Attended

The table presents the difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of the trainings they attended.

Table 10. Difference in the Competence Skills of Teachers when Grouped in terms of the Trainings they Attended

Training Attended	N	Mean Rank
INSET	66	72.36
INSET/TIP	74	68.84
Total	140	

Computed value (U): 2319.00

p-value: 0.606

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

As presented in Table 10, teachers who have attended the INSET have a mean rank of 72.36 while those who have attended INSET/TIP display a mean rank of 68.84.

Using the Mann Whitney Test, it resulted to a P- value of 0.606 at 0.05 level of significance with a computed value of 2319.00 thus, accept the null hypothesis. With the resulting data, there is no significant difference in the competence skills of teachers when grouped in terms of the trainings they attended. This finding implies that trainings attended by the elementary school teachers is not a factor of their competence skills.

The findings of this study disagree to the study of Khan & Shah (2023) which revealed that the training received by teachers have enhanced their professional competencies. The competencies of teacher can be influenced by the training or seminars that they attend or receive. Thus, their study recommends that a continuous professional training for teachers must be conducted.

It is also in contradiction to the statement of Aban et al. (2020) that professional and personal training they received can significantly affect their competence. The results of their study highlighted that the emotional intelligence of teachers as well as their personal character is affected by their trainings.

Relationship between the Level of Competence Skills of Teachers and Pupil's Academic Performance

The table presents the relationship between the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers and pupil's academic performance.

Table 11. *Relationship between the Level of Competence Skills of Teachers and Pupil's Academic Performance*

Level of Competence Skill	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very satisfactory	Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Did not meet expectation	
Very high	0	104	23	0	0	127
High	0	8	5	0	0	13
Moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	112	28	0	0	140

Computed value (G): 0.48

P-value: 0.167

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 11 shows that 127 of the respondents have a very high level of competence were 104 of the respondents' have an academic performance that is considered very satisfactory. While the remaining 23 have an academic performance that is considered satisfactory.

In terms of the relationship between the two variables, with a computed value of 0.48 and a p-value of 0.167, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the level of competence skills of elementary school teachers and pupil's academic performance.

Oredina & Ebuezza (2020) agree to this result. According to them, the competence of teachers may not be a predictor of the performance of students in their subjects

Several studies (Pamon & Oco, 2024; Ferdinand & Andala, 2023; Iqbal et al., 2019; Fauth et al., 2019; Eo, 2019) disagrees with the findings. According to them, a positive relationship was found between teachers' competence and students' academic performance. This means that the competence of teachers can promote students' academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were created:

Majority of the respondents were females, between 31- 40 years old, bachelor's degree holder with a teacher 1 position, have been teaching for 10 years and below, and have attended the INSET or In-Service Training and TIP or Teacher Induction Program.

The elementary school teachers have a very high level of competence skills when they were grouped according to their personal, management, instructional skills, and their teaching effectiveness and professionalism.

The level of pupils academic performance was very satisfactory, as they perform well academically but can still excel better.

The competence skills of elementary school teachers do not significantly vary when they are grouped according to their sex, age, highest educational attainment, teaching position, number of years in service, and trainings attended.

Competence skills of elementary school teachers do not significantly have an effect on pupils academic performance.

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were presented:

Teachers may identify their training needs so that the school can come up with an inset that can improve the developmental needs of the teachers.

The Department of Education (DepEd) may continue providing various training programs that aims to maintain a high-level competence skill among teachers.

Elementary teachers may engage students with active learning by using hands-on activities, and interactive lessons to keep students engaged and make learning fun. They may regularly attend workshops and training sessions to stay updated on the latest educational practices and innovations. Parents may engage with parents to keep them informed and involved in their children's education, reinforcing learning at home. School Heads may encourage a culture of high academic standards and continuous improvement within the school. They can foster a collaborative environment where teachers can share best practices and support each other.

Elementary Teachers may regularly seek constructive feedback from peers, students, and supervisors to improve teaching methods and classroom management. School Heads can Provide Professional Development Opportunities, Encourage Mentorship Programs and Facilitate Collaborative Environments. Education Specialists can develop and offer training programs that address specific areas for improvement based on teacher needs and current educational trends.

Although, the competence skills of elementary school teachers do not significantly have an effect on pupil's academic performance, teachers are still encouraged to pursue advanced degrees or certifications to further their expertise.

Future researchers may conduct a broader study with a larger and diverse respondent and consider different factors and skills that a competent teacher could possess.

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